

PEDAGOGICAL APPLICATION OF VISUAL AND TECHNICAL AIDS IN TEACHING
ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical importance of visual and technical aids in teaching English as a foreign language. The study examines the role of visual materials, multimedia technologies, and interactive tools in improving students’ motivation, comprehension, and communicative competence. The article also analyzes the psychological and pedagogical foundations of using visual and technical aids and their practical application in the classroom.

Key words: visual aids, technical aids, multimedia learning, English teaching, motivation, communicative competence.

INGLIZ TILINI O‘QITISHDA VIZUAL VA TEXNIK VOSITALARNING
PEDAGOGIK QO‘LLANILISHI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o‘qitishda vizual va texnik vositalarning pedagogik ahamiyatini muhokama qiladi. Tadqiqot talabalar motivatsiyasini, tushunishini va muloqot qobiliyatini oshirishda vizual materiallar, multimedia texnologiyalari va interaktiv vositalarning rolini o‘rganadi. Maqolada shuningdek, vizual va texnik vositalardan foydalanishning psixologik va pedagogik asoslari hamda ularning darsdagi amaliy qo‘llanilishi tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: vizual vositalar, texnik vositalar, multimedia orqali o‘qitish, ingliz tili o‘qitish, motivatsiya, muloqot qobiliyati

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ВИЗУАЛЬНЫХ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ
СРЕДСТВ ПРИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждается педагогическая значимость визуальных и технических средств при преподавании английского языка как иностранного. Исследование рассматривает роль визуальных материалов, мультимедийных технологий и интерактивных инструментов в повышении мотивации, понимания и коммуникативной компетенции студентов. Статья также анализирует психологические и педагогические основы использования визуальных и технических средств и их практическое применение в классе.

Ключевые слова: визуальные средства, технические средства, мультимедийное обучение, преподавание английского языка, мотивация, коммуникативная компетенция

In modern English language teaching methodology, visual and technical aids are considered essential tools that facilitate the learning process and increase its effectiveness. Since students are used to colorful, short-term videos because of modern social media tool, it is being harder and harder that keeping engaged during long traditional lessons. Therefore, using different interactive methods have become more important than just giving knowledge. The importance of visual learning was theoretically explained by Edgar Dale in his Cone of Experience theory, where he stated that learners remember more information when they see and experience things visually rather than only hearing about them.

This study researches some effective techniques and approaches that help teachers to conduct lessons more interactive, student-engaged way. As Jeremy Harmer mentioned modern language teaching should be student-centered, interactive, and communicative (Harmer, 2015). The effective use of visual and technical aids in English lessons depends not only on their availability but also on the methods and techniques applied by the teacher. Modern language teaching methodology emphasizes the integration of these aids into communicative and learner-centered activities. Properly selected techniques help to develop students' language skills, increase their motivation and create a meaningful learning environment.

One of the most widely used methods is the *presentation method*, in which visual materials are used to introduce new language items. For example, pictures, real objects and multimedia presentations help to present new vocabulary and grammatical structures in a clear and contextualized way. When students see the image of an object together with its name, they establish a direct association between the form and the meaning of the word. This makes the learning process more natural and effective. According to Allan Paivio, information is better remembered when it is presented both visually and verbally, which is known as Dual Coding Theory. When students see the image of an object together with its name, they establish a direct association between the form and the meaning of the word, which makes learning more effective.

Another important method is the *practice and drilling technique*. At this stage, visual aids such as flashcards, charts and interactive exercises are used to reinforce the newly learned material. For instance, flashcards can be used for matching words with pictures, substitution drills and memory games. These activities help learners to automatize language structures and improve their pronunciation. A famous scientist Jim Scrivener, practice activities should be meaningful, visual, and interactive in order to improve language acquisition.

The *communicative method* also relies on visual and technical aids. Pictures, videos and situational illustrations are used as prompts for pair work, group discussions, role plays and storytelling. Such tasks encourage students to express their own ideas, describe events and solve problems using the target language. In this way, visual materials serve as a stimulus for real communication in the classroom. This approach supports communicative competence and learner autonomy.

Audio-visual materials are especially effective for developing **listening and speaking skills**. Through watching videos, films and listening to authentic audio recordings, students are exposed to natural speech, different accents and real-life communicative situations. Pre-listening and pre-viewing activities help learners to predict the content, while post-listening tasks develop comprehension and speaking skills.

Another effective technique is the use of visual aids for **developing productive skills**. For example, a series of pictures can be used for writing a story, describing a process or expressing an opinion. Mind maps and diagrams help students to organize their ideas before speaking or writing. In this way, visual support improves both the content and the structure of students' speech.

Technical aids also play a crucial role in organizing **interactive learning**. The use of multimedia projectors, interactive whiteboards and online platforms allows teachers to create

quizzes, language games and virtual exercises. These tools provide immediate feedback and promote learner autonomy. Moreover, they make it possible to implement blended and distance learning, which has become particularly important in modern education. ‘These tools provide immediate feedback and increase student motivation’ says Mayer.

The selection of methods and techniques should correspond to the stages of the lesson. At the presentation stage visual aids are used for introducing new material, at the practice stage for reinforcing it, and at the production stage for developing communicative competence. Therefore, the teacher should carefully plan how and when to use each type of aid.

In conclusion, visual and technical aids are most effective when they are used through appropriate pedagogical methods and techniques. Their integration into English lessons makes the learning process more interactive, communicative and student-centered. As a result, learners develop their language skills more successfully and become active participants in the educational process.

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